

Tutorial

This is the diagram we're going to use to graphically configure the next scripts.

In the right-hand column, you can see all diagram features in alphabetical order, divided into groups. Navigate these groups by clicking on one element and scroll. On the bottom screen, we can configure the attributes of each pipeline feature on the 'Page' section.

Configuration

Start by defining Pipeline version as **2.1**.

Then, create a **Docker Executor** in Pipeline Tools by clicking or dragging this element onto the diagram. Navigate Pipeline Tools by clicking on one element and scroll until you find **Docker Executor**. This executor is named **default**, with image **cimg/node:its** and **medium** resourceClass.

Docker Executor is in Pipeline Tools because it is a Pipeline tool.

Now create a **Job** in Pipeline Tools named **install-dependencies** that reuses **default** executor.

Following the same logic, Job is also a Pipeline tool.

This Job has a **RestoreCache Step** in Job Tools with keys: **dependencies-{{ checksum "package.json" }}**. RestoreCache Step is a Job tool and is therefore in the Job Tools section.

The **keys** attribute is a list and to correctly change this list we will:

1. Input a new key in **New Key Input**
2. Click on **Add key** button

Add another key to understand how to remove one:

1. Type **test** and click on **Add key** button
2. In **Keys** list, select **test** and click on **Remove key**

This Job also has a **SaveCache Step** in Job Tools with paths: **~/.cache/yarn** and **node_modules** and with key: **dependencies-{{ checksum "package.json" }}**. **NOTE** that paths is also an enumeration.

To finish, create a **Workflow** in Pipeline Tools named **build-and-deploy** and version **2.1**.

This Workflow has a JobWorkflow in Workflow Tools named **install-dependencies**

You now finished the tutorial!